

GEOGRAFIYA FANINI O'QITISHNING LOYIHAVIY VA INNOVATSION USULLARI

¹Kozhabekova Zakhida Ersultanovna, ²Кожобекова Захида Ерсултановна,

³Kozhabekova Zakhida Ersultanovna, Yerimkhan Zarina

¹geografiya fanlari nomzodi, dotsent vazifasini bajaruvchi, ²к.г.н., и.о. доцента, ³Candidate of geographic sciences, associate professor

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Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqolada geografiya fanini o'qitishda loyihaviy va innovatsion usullar samaradorligi ko'rib chiqiladi. Loyihaviy usul o'quvchilarning tadqiqot va jamoaviy ish qobiliyatlarini rivojlantiradi. Innovatsion usullar, masalan, raqamli xaritalar va geoaxborot tizimlari ta'lim materialini ko'rinadigan tarzda taqdim etib, qiziqishni oshiradi. Taqqoslash tahlili usullarni birgalikda qo'llashni taklif qiladi.

Аннотация. В данной статье рассматривается эффективность проектных и инновационных методов обучения географии. Проектный метод направлен на развитие у учащихся исследовательских и командных навыков. Инновационные методы, такие как цифровые карты и геоинформационные системы, позволяют наглядно представлять учебный материал и повышают интерес к предмету. Сравнительный анализ методов предлагает их совместное применение.

Annotation. This article discusses the effectiveness of project-based and innovative methods in teaching geography. The project method focuses on developing students' research and teamwork skills. Innovative methods, such as digital maps and geographic information systems, enable visual presentation of educational material and increase interest in the subject. A comparative analysis suggests the joint application of these methods.

Kalit so'zlar: Geografiyani o'qitish, loyihaviy usul, innovatsion usullar, raqamli xaritalar, GAZ, virtual haqiqat, ta'lim samaradorligi, o'quvchilarning tadqiqot qobiliyatlari.

Ключевые слова: обучение географии, проектный метод, инновационные методы, цифровые карты, ГИС, виртуальная реальность, эффективность обучения, исследовательские навыки учащихся.

Keywords: teaching geography, project-based method, innovative methods, digital maps, GIS, virtual reality, teaching effectiveness, students' research skills.

The subject of geography plays a significant role in the modern education system. Through this subject, students not only understand natural and social processes but also develop perspectives on global issues, enhance their ecological awareness, and learn to respect their environment. Today, the advancement of information technologies and innovative methods is creating a new perspective on teaching methodologies and changing students' learning approaches. This particularly emphasizes the importance of using project-based and innovative methods in geography education. These methods awaken students' cognitive interests, increase their engagement in lessons, and teach them to think independently and make decisions.

This article reviews project-based and innovative methods in teaching geography. The main objective is to analyze the significance of these methods in the educational process and their impact on students' learning. Additionally, the article aims to demonstrate the advantages of implementing project-based and innovative approaches and to suggest key ways of applying them.

Project-based and innovative methods are considered active approaches to teaching within the education system. The project method focuses on students acquiring knowledge while solving real-world problems. This method encourages the development of research skills and stimulates creative thinking. Innovative methods involve the integration of new technologies and teaching methodologies, reorganizing the teaching process in a novel way. Tools such as digital maps, virtual and augmented reality, and geographic information systems (GIS) are frequently used in these methods.

The project-based teaching method originated in the early 20th century from the ideas of educators like John Dewey and William Kilpatrick. They supported connecting knowledge with real-life experiences. In the 20th century, this method was introduced into various subjects and is now widely used in geography education. The development of innovative methods is directly linked to the integration of new technologies. These methods align with 21st-century educational trends, as modern students learn in digital environments and develop their capabilities through them.

In Kazakhstan, research is being conducted on the use of project-based and innovative methods in teaching geography. Scientific studies demonstrate the effectiveness of these methods in enhancing the quality of students' education and increasing interest in the geography subject. Furthermore, foreign research has highlighted the significance of project-based and innovative methods in developing students' spatial thinking abilities and ecological consciousness in geography education. The project-based teaching method aims to direct students toward purposeful learning and allows them to independently acquire knowledge. Its core principles are student engagement, creativity, and fostering individual inquiry. In project work, students explore real problems and strive to find solutions. Projects can vary in relation to the topic: research projects, problem-solving projects, creative projects, and mixed projects.

The project method promotes students' independent learning and helps develop their research skills. It fosters teamwork, critical thinking, and a sense of responsibility. However, this method requires significant time and preparation from teachers, as well as support for students' interests and engagement. Through the project method, students enhance their critical thinking abilities and learn problem-solving approaches. They work in groups, improve their interpersonal skills, and learn to take responsibility independently.

Table 1 - Description of Innovative Methods in Teaching Geography and Examples of Application

Innovative Method	Description	Examples Application	of Impact Knowledge	on Teacher's Role	Student's Role
Digital Maps	Teaching geography through interactive maps and apps	Mapping applications, Google Earth	Increases interest in the subject, develops spatial thinking	Provides guidance selecting using apps	Explores maps, conducts independent analysis
Geographic Information Systems (GIS)	Tools for analyzing and visualizing geographic data	ArcGIS, QGIS, ecological studies	Teaches deeper understanding of geographic processes and data handling	Teaches fundamentals and provides direction	Works with GIS data, studies geographical objects

Virtual Reality (VR)	Virtual trips to natural areas	Virtual excursions, e.g., visiting volcanoes	Helps visualize material, increases interest	Manages tools and provides support	Engages in the virtual world, participates actively
Augmented Reality (AR)	Adding digital information to real objects for interactive study	digital AR apps for demonstrating climatic processes	Allows viewing geographic processes "live"	Teaches how to work with AR tools	Studies objects through AR, develops observation skills
Mobile Applications	Apps for interactive teaching of geography	Environmental apps, weather monitoring programs	Increases interest in the subject, teaches application of knowledge	Advises and guides on choosing applications	Works independently with apps, applies knowledge
Digital Games and Simulations	Teaching geographic processes through interactive games and simulations	Climate and landscape modeling games	Increases motivation to learn, aids understanding complex concepts	Helps in selecting and providing direction	Participates in modeling, and develops critical thinking

Project-based and innovative methods play a significant role in the educational process, each with its unique features and application strategies. A comparative analysis of these methods highlights key aspects such as effectiveness, implementation complexity, and the roles of teachers and students.

Project-based methods assist students in independent learning and developing research skills, as they directly engage in solving real-world problems and contribute their insights. This approach facilitates a deeper understanding of the material and reinforces learning through practical experience. In contrast, innovative methods—such as virtual reality, geographic information systems (GIS), and digital maps—present educational material in a visual and interactive manner, making it easier to comprehend complex topics and increasing interest in the subject.

The implementation of project-based methods requires significant time and preparation from teachers, as each project needs to be organized in advance and systematically planned. Innovative methods, on the other hand, often depend on technological resources and may require technical support for teachers. To effectively utilize these tools, both teachers and students should undergo specialized training.

In project-based methods, teachers serve as project leaders and guides, while students take on active participant and researcher roles. In innovative methods, teachers act as instructors who support the use of technology and monitor students' engagement in the process. In this context, students learn to explore new technologies independently and expand their knowledge through interactive activities.

Project-based methods develop individual and group work skills, teaching students to think independently and make decisions autonomously. However, they require time and organization

for implementation. Innovative methods offer engaging and visual presentations of material, but they necessitate specific resources due to technological dependencies.

To enhance the effectiveness of these methods, it is recommended to combine them. For instance, using innovative tools (such as GIS or digital maps) in project-based research can deepen students' understanding and make the learning process more engaging.

Several recommendations can be made for teachers to effectively apply project-based and innovative methods:

1. **Organizing Project Work:** Teachers should plan projects and select topics that interest students. Choosing projects that allow for creative thinking and independent decision-making will be more effective.
2. **Applying Innovative Methods:** Utilizing interactive tools and technologies can increase students' interest in lessons. For example, digital maps and GIS tools can be used for regional studies, while virtual reality and augmented reality tools are effective for visualizing natural objects and processes.
3. **Providing Support for Learning:** During the use of project-based and innovative methods, teachers are advised to select appropriate tools and resources. For instance, using ArcGIS, Google Earth, and various ecological monitoring applications can make lessons more interactive and engaging.

The analysis of project-based and innovative methods presented in this article demonstrates their unique advantages and significance in improving the teaching process. Project-based methods develop students' research capabilities, teaching them to think critically, make decisions, and consider problems comprehensively. This approach also contributes to strengthening their sense of responsibility and teamwork skills.

Innovative methods, particularly the use of digital technologies and geographic information systems, facilitate students' visual understanding of educational material and help them grasp complex processes in a clear and engaging manner. Such methods enhance students' interest in the subject and aid in material retention.

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